

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added Course 2020-21 academic year for BPT

DIET AND NUTRITION

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added course
Diet & Nutrition

OBJECTIVES

1. To provide students with the knowledge of basic terminology of nutrition & the functions of food in healthy life sustenance.
2. To impart knowledge about the food classification and role of special functional food.
3. To equip students with knowledge and understanding of modern aspects of nutritional science.

**FOR BPT STUDENTS
(2019 BATCH)**

**15 WEEKS
(2 HOURS/WEEK)**

**ONLINE SESSIONS USING ZOOM
PLATFORM**

FOR MORE INFORMATION:

Phone: 0824-2429139
City campus, ground floor, Pandeshwar,
Mangaluru
www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in
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Course period	From June till September 2020 (online), during 3 rd semester (15 weeks)
Duration	30 hours (2 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	BPT 2 nd year undergraduates (2019 batch)

Course Aims:

The course is aimed to enable students to gain knowledge about interaction between food, body and health under normal and special circumstances.

Course Objectives:

- To provide students with the knowledge of basic terminology and several aspects of nutrition and the functions of food in healthy life sustenance;
- To impart knowledge about the food classification, nutrition during special conditions and role of special functional food;
- To equip students with knowledge and understanding of modern aspects of nutritional science and novel food usage.

Course Outcomes:

A successful completion of this course will enable students to:

- ✓ Summarize and critically discuss/ understand both fundamental and applied aspects of food science. They will be able to explain functions of specific nutrients in maintaining health, identifying nutrient specific foods and apply principles from the various facets of food science and related disciplines to solve practical as well as real-world problems.
- ✓ Use current information technologies to locate and apply evidence-based guidelines and protocols and get imparted with critical thinking to take leadership roles in fields of health, dietetics, special nutritional needs and nutritional counseling.

Course Outline:

Week	Lectures	Assignments	Hour ¹
Module 1 «Basics of Food Science»			
1-5	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Basic definition, function, classification and dietary sources of foods, nutrition and dietetics.• Concept of malnutrition, health, immunity by food and functions of food.• Classification of macronutrients and micronutrients• Is water a nutrient?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">✓ Self-Study✓ Home Assignments	10
Module 2 «Effect of nutraceuticals on health»			

6-10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to chemistry of prebiotics and probiotics as functional foods • Effect of nutraceuticals on health and prevention of diseases • Beneficiary microbes and their metabolism for improving health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Self-Study ✓ Home Assignments 	10
Module 3 «Nutrition during extremes and novel foods»			
11-15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutritional principles of adaptation during special circumstances of weather, professions and diseases • Nutrition for high physical work • Sports nutrition • Introduction to novel foods, functional foods and organic foods • Beneficial and harmful effects of genetically modified food 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Home Assignments ✓ To devise a food plan for a female athlete who is into track events. ✓ To devise a food plan for a 32 year old male who is into body building 	10

¹ Hours designed for Classroom sessions, video tutorials, Home Assignments, Activities etc.

Attendance Policy

The course requires compulsory 75% attendance and only in this case a student will be issued a certificate.

Book References:

1. Maureen Zimmerman and Beth. An introduction to nutrition. Vol. 1
2. Nutrition and Dietetics by Sheila John, Sadhana Rajmohan, S. Karthiga, B.S Vasanthi
3. Jim Mann, A. Stewart Truswell. Essentials of Human Nutriti

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

ABDUL AMEEN RASHID (5SU19PT001)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

ABHAYASREE M (5SU19PT002)

for attending and completing the value added course on

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

ADITHYA M (5SU19PT003)

for attending and completing the value added course on

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June to September 2020

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Course Instructor**

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

AHAMMED NASEEH V B (5SU19PT004)

for attending and completing the value added course on

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Course Instructor**

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Certificate of Completion

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AISHWARYA BIJUSH (5SU19PT005)

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Certificate of Completion

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ALBIN JACOB VARUGHESE (5SU19PT006)

for attending and completing the value added course on

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Certificate of Completion

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ANAMIKA K (5SU19PT007)

for attending and completing the value added course on

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June to September 2020

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Certificate of Completion

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ANJANA MANOJ (5SU19PT008)

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ANJANA MOHAN (5SU19PT009)

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ANJIMA K V (5SU19PT010)

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Certificate of Completion

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ATHIRA P KRISHNA (5SU19PT011)

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June to September 2020

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Course Instructor**

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Certificate of Completion

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AYESHA SAFEERA (5SU19PT012)

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Certificate of Completion

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BAGHELE AISHWARYA RAJESH (5SU19PT014)

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Certificate of Completion

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BENECIA ANITA CARDOZO (5SU19PT015)

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BHAVYASHREE C VAIDYA (5SU19PT016)

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CHANNAMMA R NELAGUDDA (5SU19PT017)

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CHARAN JITENDRA VAIDYA (5SU19PT018)

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CHAUHAN KAVITA BABURAM (5SU19PT019)

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DANY ELDHOSE (5SU19PT020)

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DEEPTHI K J (5SU19PT021)

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DI – ANN VERA VAZ (5SU19PT022)

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DIAS RICHA CHRISTINE (5SU19PT023)

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FARSANA T (5SU19PT024)

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FATHIMA (5SU19PT025)

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FATHIMA ARSANA (5SU19PT026)

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FATHIMABI (5SU19PT027)

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FINU ANTONY (5SU19PT028)

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GIFIN M PAUL (5SU19PT029)

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GOKUL A P (5SU19PT030)

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Certificate of Completion

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GREESHMA M EDWIN (5SU19PT031)

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Certificate of Completion

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HARSHITHA G S (5SU19PT032)

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Certificate of Completion

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HAZEBA FATHIMA (5SU19PT033)

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Certificate of Completion

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HEMANTH A V (5SU19PT034)

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HRUTHIKA M (5SU19PT035)

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IFTHISHAM (5SU19PT036)

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Certificate of Completion

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JANE CARYN LOBO (5SU19PT037)

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JILSHA P Y (5SU19PT038)

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JITHIN T (5SU19PT039)

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JOYCE MARIAM JOSY (5SU19PT040)

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Certificate of Completion

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KARUNA VISHRAM PARAB (5SU19PT041)

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Certificate of Completion

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KRISHNAPRIYA BIJU (5SU19PT042)

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Certificate of Completion

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LUGELLE MARIA DE GRACA FERNANDES (5SU19PT043)

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MARIYAMMA (5SU19PT044)

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MEHTAB JUBAPU SHUAIB (5SU19PT045)

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MOHAMMED TAHA (5SU19PT046)

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MUHAMMED RASIL P M (5SU19PT047)

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

MUHAMMED SINAN K (5SU19PT049)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

MUHAMMED SHANID P (5SU19PT050)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

MUHSIN K.P (5SU19PT051)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

NEELINA K (5SU19PT052)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'S. Rajasekar'.

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

NIRMAL JAIN (5SU19PT053)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

Handwritten signature of Dr. Sanya A in blue ink.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

PEARL ASTIDA D'SA (5SU19PT054)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

PRIYANTH A (5SU19PT055)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

PUSHPA N NAYAK (5SU19PT056)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

RAGHAVENDRA A N (5SU19PT057)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

RAHUL E S (5SU19PT058)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

RATHIKA RAVINDRA NAYAK (5SU19PT059)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Sanya'.

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

RAVI R H (5SU19PT060)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

REMYA RAVEENDRAN (5SU19PT061)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

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RIFNA KOUSAR (5SU19PT062)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

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RINSHIDA N P (5SU19PT063)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

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SAIDH ALI HAMZA (5SU19PT064)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

SANDRA K R (5SU19PT065)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SANGAR SHIVANI NAVIN (5SU19PT066)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SANGEETH SANTHOSH (5SU19PT067)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SAYED FARZANA PARVEEN (5SU19PT068)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SEBINNABI TOR GAL (5SU19PT069)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SHAHISTHA BANU (5SU19PT070)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

SHAIKH SUMERA MEHEK NASEEM IRFAN (5SU19PT071)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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SHAJAHAN (5SU19PT072)

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June to September 2020

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Course Instructor**

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SHIFANA M E (5SU19PT073)

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June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

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SHRAMIKA (5SU19PT074)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

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SHRIRAKSHA R ANGADI (5SU19PT075)

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June to September 2020

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Course Instructor**

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Dean**

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Certificate of Completion

presented to

STACY SANTAN FERNANDES (5SU19PT076)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
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Certificate of Completion

presented to

SWETHA P S (5SU19PT077)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor

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Dean

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COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

SYED MOHAMMED S J (5SU19PT078)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

TIDKE ANIKET NIRAJ (5SU19PT079)

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June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

VARSHINI B (5SU19PT080)

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"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

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**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

YASSER K V (5SU19PT081)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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**Dr. Sanya A
Course Instructor**

Handwritten signature of Dr. S. Rajasekar in blue ink.

**Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean**

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Certificate of Completion

presented to

ZAHWA MUNEER (5SU19PT082)

for attending and completing the value added course on

"Diet and Nutrition"

June to September 2020

Total Hours- 30 (online)

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Course Instructor**

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